

A Treasure Trove about Vietnam's Vibrant Cultural Nuances

Amazon Book Review Series of "*Wild Wise Weird*"

GP & Mumbi

United States, January 21, 2025

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Fresh and engaging

The mix of previously published and new stories keeps the collection fresh and engaging, making it a treasure trove for anyone curious about Vietnam's vibrant cultural nuances. This book is a rare gem that balances humor with profound reflections on human values. Highly recommended!

GP

★★★★★ **Fresh and engaging**

Reviewed in the United States on January 21, 2025

Verified Purchase

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Screenshot. Review of "*Wild Wise Weird*" by GP [1]. Reviewed in the United States on January 21, 2024.

An interesting collection of fables

The book has a collection of short stories with an interesting writing style that has lots of humor.

I totally love the stories in this book of the kingfisher and his community of birds. there is plenty to learn from in each story and plenty to laugh about as well.

There are also images of birds for each stories some a hand drawn and painted and make the book a wonderful art work too.

Highly recommend if you love usual stories with humor

Mumbi

★★★★★ **An interesting collection of fables**

Reviewed in the United States on January 22, 2025

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Screenshot. Review of “*Wild Wise Weird*” by Mumbi [2]. Reviewed in the United States on January 21, 2024.

(Note: This paper reprints of GP’s and Mumbi’s reviews [1,2] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [3]. The reprint’s title is created based on the review’s content.*

References

[1] GP. (2025, Jan. 21). Fresh and engaging. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R264N17AEJBQZ3/>

[2] Mumbi. (2025, Jan. 21). An interesting collection of fables. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R4LF103L6U9D4/>

[3] Vuong, Q. H. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6/>